

Impact of Help Lines on Farmers with Respect to Jalgaon District

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Abstract- Helpline may be Helpline number or an helpline application which distributes knowledge and guidance to Farmers to increase their productivity. The increased usage of help lines turned to be a guide to Farmers. This paper focuses on understanding experimental viewpoint about intensity, usage of help lines and its impact on the Farmers and their Farm's productivity. Instead of Helpline centers, it is much enhancing and effective to Farmers. For instance Farmers get to know solution to problems and guidance of how to resolve that problems. Farmers need not to roam in search of Helpline centers.

It is very user friendly and easy to get initiated. Simply enter telephone number and call on helpline. Helpline numbers are Toll Free numbers, so Farmers need not to pay any charges. Also Helpline applications are offline applications, so Farmers does not need any internet connection.

With Help lines, resolving farming problems has become much easier, faster and cheaper. It is less expensive as compared to Helpline centers. An individual can easily access Helpline facilities to increase their productivity.

Helplines provide detailed knowledge of farming. Helpline provide information w.r.t. Country and District and also Farmers can choose language which they understand. It helps farmers which crop should be suitable for current weather and quantity of fertilizers and pesticides required for crops production. It provides detailed and understandable process of production of each and every crop w.r.t. season and weather. Also, market rate of crops, profit and loss which helps farmers to know which crop should be produce. Farmers can search for Pesticide and farm machinery dealers, seed and fertilizer dealers. Blog provides expert's advice which helps farmers in production.

Keywords- *Help lines , Help lines for farmers , app for farmers , agricultural helpline toll free number, farmer portal, kisan help lines services, agriculture website list, etc*

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent advancements in technology have changed our lives significantly. Most noticeably, they facilitate our living, as evidenced by more effectiveness, efficiency, convenience, and ease which result from their proper application. With the aid of recent advanced technologies, difficult tasks can be accomplished in less time with less effort and energy than they were in the past. Many people praise their technological gadgets that they use in their everyday lives. Many of us depend on it to get us through the day, to do our job, to get around, and to find certain things.

Besides all, this Application is highly addictive and can create a great impact on regular users, and apart from that it can leave a trace that becomes difficult to control and cure.

Mostly Helpline android applications are used rather than Telephonic help lines and its updates provides more functionality since its release date. The main purpose behind this application is to replace call functionality with a cross platform mobile messenger that works on an internet data plan.

It is currently available for iPhone, android, windows phone, Nokia symbian, etc. Helpline android application uses Location only, Internet required for few functionalities only. Telephonic help lines uses mobile networks and it does not charge any call rates. Also, its provides information via SMS service.

It is popular because there is no cost for information and guidance other than the Location. It is easy to get started. Simply enter the location and telephone

number to the device into the application. It then sorts through the location and displays all information of all crops available on that location. Also, it provides market rates of crops and financial states of market.

- To understand and Identify the Help lines available for Farmers
- To know awareness of Help lines w.r.t Farmers
- To identify the use of Help lines w.r.t Farmers

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Helpline may be Helpline number or an helpline application which provides guidance to Farmers to increase their productivity. Channel Saam TV provides farming show AGROWAN in which farmers share their own experiences and opinions and provide solutions for problems which they are facing.

Umang is a largest program executed by Government for farmers which helpful to them for more productivity.

KrishiVigyan Kendra is an Institution which provides knowledge and guidance for farmers. Government also provide some Toll free number help lines such as

- Kissan call center (18001801551)
- National Helpline for Farmers (18002006821)

III. OBJECTIVES

The preliminary study examines the use of Help lines amongst farmers in Jalgaon District. The researchers attempted to understand the perceived high-level of usage of Help lines amongst the farmers by looking at the intensity of its usage and how it affects their productivity.

V. RESEARCH QUESTIONS FOR FARMERS

1. Demographic Data - Personal Details

Name: _____	Age: _____
Date of Birth: _____	Education: _____
Address: _____	
City: _____	Country: _____
Pin code: _____	Mobile No.: _____

2. Are you a Smartphone user?
 - Yes
 - No
3. Do you use internet?
 - Yes
 - No
4. How frequently you use internet?
 - Daily
 - Twice in a day
 - Once in a week
 - Once in a month
5. Are you aware of Help lines?
 - Yes
 - No

This statistics shows Agricultural production of 7 states which is yeilds in kg per hectare till 2016. In above statistics, India stands on 4th position. [3]

IV. HYPOTHESIS

- H1: There is no correlation between awareness and utilization of Help lines
- H2: There is positive correlation between awareness and utilization of Help lines.
- H3: There is no correlation between utilization and productivity.
- H4: There is positive correlation between utilization and productivity.
- H5: There is no correlation between accessibility and Help lines.
- H6: There is positive correlation between accessibility and Help lines.

6. Which Android helpline applications are most useful to you?
 - RML
 - UMANG
 - KISSAN
 - FARM RISE
 - AGRO STAR
 - KHETI BADI
 - KRISHI KING
 - KRISHI GYAN
 - KRISHI KENDRA
 - KISSAN MARKET
 - KISSAN SUVIDHA
 - IFFCO KISAAN
 - AGRICULTURE
 - CROP INSURANCE
7. How many times do you visit Android helpline applications?
 - Only 1
 - More than 5
 - Less than 10
 - Many more times
8. Which method you are using for getting helpline facilities?
 - Toll Free Numbers
 - Android Applications
9. How many types of crops you produce at a time?
 - Single
 - Double
 - Thrice
10. Which crops you take in highest production?
 - Lime
 - Maize
 - Udid
 - Mung
 - Bajara
 - Banana
 - Cotton
 - Wheat
 - Peanut
 - Millet
 - Sugarcane
 - Sorghum [12]
11. When you think about Help lines ,do you think of it is productive?
 - Yes
 - No
12. Do you feel these Help lines are really helpful to you?
 - Yes
 - No
13. How satisfied are you with the reliability of this Help lines?
 - Likely
 - Most Likely
 - Unlikely
 - Most Unlikely

VI. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

➤ Data Collection

Primary Data:

Survey forms are distributed to farmers for data collection. Survey forms contains Questionnaire session. The reasons were:

1. To ascertain whether the questions chosen will be relevant in addressing the set objectives of the research and also to update questionnaire and discard irrelevant questions.
2. To debug errors before the actual questionnaires go out to the actual respondents.

3. To calculate the average response rate in the use of various medium for data collection.

We have prepared semi-open ended questions were developed. The semi-open-ended questions placed no restrictions on how research participants could respond to the questions. Participants responded in their own words and were not constrained to select their responses from a list of choices like the closed ended questions.

Secondary Data:

Secondary research methodology defined as Data which were gathered from diverse sources, including, archival sources, textbooks, journals/articles (both publish and unpublished), and internet sites.

In secondary research methodology for research, we refer Help lines provided by Government of Maharashtra such as

1. Kissan call center (18001801551)
2. National Helpline for Farmers (18002006821)
3. KrishiVigyan Kendra
4. RCF Farmer care
5. Umang Application provided by Government of India

Also, Show on Saam TV channel named as AGROWAN which helps farmers for increasing productivity.

➤ Sample Size

The population under-study which consists of farmers in Jalgaon District is vast, making it impossible to interview and administer questionnaire to the whole population. As a result, a part of the population referred to as sample was taken for the study. Hundred (100) representatives from particular villages in Jalgaon Districts were surveyed. The number included hundred (100) farmers interviewed.

VII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter analyses the responses given by respondents through the administration of structured questionnaire conducted. In order to make interpretation and analysis easier, tables are presented first, followed by its interpretation and analysis using Chi-Square test.

(Table I)

Distribution of Helpline Users	Number of Helpline Users	Percentage
Helpline Users(Through call)	63	63%
Helpline Users(Through android application)	37	37%
Total	100	100%

The table I represent the number of farmers interviewed on various small villages from Jalgaon District w. r. t. their education. Out of these,30% represent farmers who uses Telephonic Help lines

while 70% farmers who uses help lines provided using android application.

Out of the total number of farmers interviewed, 70 of the farmers which represent 70% of the interviewers said they use the Telephonic helpline for resolving their issues, but sometimes due to network issues they are not able to contact. Most of the farmers prefer both android applications as well as Toll free help lines.

80% of Farmers said it has positive impact on their productivity.

Telephonic Help lines which are highly used in Jalgaon District as per survey are

1. KISSAN CALL CENTER(18001801551)
2. National Helpline for Farmers (18002006821)

Most commonly used android application Help lines in Jalgaon Districts as per survey are

1. RML
2. KISSAN
3. KRISHI KING
4. KRISHI SUVIDHA

(Table II)

Education	Number of Farmers	Percentage
SSC	45	45%
HSC	25	25%
GRADUATE	30	30%
Total	100	100%

The table II above represent the education of farmers interviewed on various small villages from Jalgaon District w. r. t. type of help lines they are using. Out of these, 48% represent farmers who are SSC passed while 30% farmers who are graduates. The above table is formed by analysis and interpretation using Chi-Square test.

Above table indicates that SSC and HSC passed people can utilize help lines facilities as better as graduates does. Education does not matter for utilizing helpline facilities. Due to user friendly facilities any farmer whether he/she is well educated or not can understand and utilize helpline facilities.

The table III indicates usage of Help lines where data is collected by executing survey within Farmers in Jalgaon District and count and percentage is calculated using Chi-Square tests.

(Table III)

Usage of Help lines	Count	Percentage(%)
Daily	13	13%
Twice in a day	55	55%
Once in a week	28	28%
Weekly	1	1%
Once in a month	3	3%

The table IV represents productivity with respect to usage of Help lines calculated using Chi-Square test.

(Table IV)

Productivity increased or not	Count	Percentage (%)
Yes(Productive increased)	96	96%
No(No Productivity increased)	4	4%

(Chart 1)

(Chart 2)

The pie chart(chart 1) is calculated and analyzed by Chi-Square test with respect to Farmer’s education and types of Help lines and vice versa where data is collected by executing survey within Farmers from Jalgaon District.

The pie chart (chart 2) is calculated and analyzed by Chi-Square test with respect to Usage of Help lines and their Help line’s usage and vice versa where data

is collected by executing survey within Farmers from Jalgaon District.

VIII. CONCLUSION

From preceding discussion, Help lines are useful for farmers to increase their productivity. Most commonly farmers use telephonic help lines due ease of access anytime and anywhere. It does not need Smartphone or internet for accessing telephonic help lines.

There are few android application helpline users. Also, as per survey there are 5 peoples out of 100 farmers which are unaware of help lines. They prefer seminars conducted by Government for farmer’s guidance.

As per survey and result, it concludes that less educated farmers are highly use these help lines. That is for the utilization of help lines, education is not necessary. People in rural area can also be use these help lines and it provides language compatibility.

IX. RECOMMENDATIONS

- Awareness raising** is an important task and an outcome of the service provided by help lines. These efforts should be reinforced to inform farmers about the role of and the services. They provide in order Help lines to build wider public awareness on the issues and the resources/facilities available.
- Methods for promoting information** about the Help lines. Information can be advertised through national media platforms, such as television, radio, or programs and posters, or conducting seminars.
- Extend the target groups of audiences in advertising helpline activities:** The impact of awareness raising is greatly enhanced if clear targets of the awareness activities are identified, for example farmers, celebrities, etc.
- Take help of the media:** Engaging the support of the media in raising awareness considerably broadens the impact and reduces the cost.
- Language:** Awareness messages are most effective when they adopt the language best understood by the farmers.
- Organize Government Programs/Government Support:** Every effort should be made to involve the participation of government agencies in spreading the messages to reach a large group of people. In that way, Help lines will be able to gain

more attention and help inform policies in this field.[1]

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